

Research on Green Supply Chain Strategy of Pakistan from the Perspective of Circular Economy

Muhammad Asif Abbas ✉

School of Economics and Management, Taiyuan University of Science and Technology, China

Bin Qiao ✉

School of Economics and Management, Taiyuan University of Science and Technology, China

Kashif Bashir

School of Economics and Management, Taiyuan University of Science and Technology, China

Rumaisa Rafiq

Department of Home Sciences, MNS University of Agriculture, Pakistan

Qanmber Ali Shah

School of Management Science, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan, Pakistan

Zubair Niaz

Department of Arts, University of Peshawar, Pakistan

Abstract

The development of Pakistan's leather product manufacturing industry is plagued by issues such as resource scarcity, increasing leather waste, and worsening environmental pollution. Under the promotion of circular economy policies, green supply chain management, as an effective management practice, is one of the important management strategies for the green development of Pakistan's manufacturing industry. There are many risks in the green supply chain that have a significant impact on the leather production and operation of enterprises. The difficulty in finding green suppliers and the low response level to customer demand have become bottlenecks for the development of green supply chains in the leather product manufacturing industry. In order to establish a good cooperative relationship between enterprises, suppliers, and customers, enterprises can implement supply chain integration, while also helping to rationalize green supply chain resources, increase their competitive advantage, and create value for the enterprise. On this basis, a theoretical model for the integration capability of green supply chain in leather product manufacturing industry was constructed, and four research hypotheses were proposed. Then, this article used a questionnaire survey method to obtain 200 valid questionnaires from leather product manufacturing enterprises. Additionally, this study provides some management insights for the improvement of green supply chain management in Pakistan's leather product manufacturing industry, and offers a new perspective for promoting the steady growth of Pakistan's green supply chain and the high-quality development of circular economy.

Keywords: *circular economy, Green supply chain risk control, Supply chain integration, leather product manufacturing industry.*

JEL Classification codes: *E51, Q21.*

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Introduction

Pakistan is a major consumer and manufacturer of leather products, occupying an important position in the global leathers market. With the reduction of leather product manufacturing costs and the acceleration of update speed, serious environmental pollution has been brought about, accelerating the scarcity of resources. However, with the rapid growth of the consumer leathers market, effective recycling and reuse of leather waste remains a major challenge. Compared with the linear increase in net consumption of resources in traditional industrial economy, circular economy increases production by reducing resource waste and recycling resources. The successful implementation of circular economy is considered a feasible way for Pakistan to achieve "leapfrog development" in environmental protection and remedy the environmental damage usually caused by rapid industrialization (Chen, et al., 2023; Geng, & Doberstein, 2008).

As one of the five development concepts of the 13th Five Year Plan, "green" has attracted more attention from the government and enterprises towards the green development of the manufacturing industry (Riley, et al., 2016). But many environmental problems should not be solely attributed to the enterprise itself, as they are closely related to its upstream and downstream supply chains. Based on the current strong promotion of circular economy in the country, introducing green supply chains in the production of leather products can reduce the pressure that the environment brings to enterprises. Therefore, more manufacturing companies are implementing green supply chain management practices, such as Huawei's "Green Partner" certification program, which reduces environmental pollution and resource waste through joint efforts with upstream and downstream companies in the supply chain, thereby achieving the goal of green development for enterprises (Soosay, Hyland, & Ferrer, 2008).

Nevertheless, rapid environmental changes may pose risks for businesses when implementing green supply chain practices. The process of implementing a green supply chain is complex, as procurement, operations, and services all require environmental commitments, thus green supply chain management faces different risks (Chiang, & Chuang, 2024). In order to cope with green supply chain risks, enterprises must respond quickly to uncertainties in the supply chain and utilize their capabilities to gain competitive advantages. Supply chain integration is considered a powerful concept for managing risks and addressing uncertainty. Supply chain integration requires companies and all their supply chain partners to work towards the same goal, establishing effective communication, resource sharing, and risk and return systems (Rasheed, et al., 2024).

There is relatively little academic research on the relationship between supply chain integration capability and supply chain risk control. Practitioners of leather product manufacturing enterprises implementing green supply chains find it difficult to solve such problems encountered in green supply chain management. Main contributions of this work are:

- This article mainly studies the impact of risk control on the improvement of supply chain integration capability?
- How does the improvement of supply chain integration capability affect enterprise performance?

- This study establishes a theoretical model of green supply chain integration capability in the leather product manufacturing industry from the perspective of the rapidly developing circular economy model.

It explores the relationship between green supply chain risk control and supply chain integration capability, as well as their impact on enterprise performance. It provides some suggestions for the development of green supply chain in Pakistan's leather product enterprises and also promotes the rapid development of circular economy model in the manufacturing industry. From a theoretical perspective, there is relatively little research in Pakistan on the relationship between green supply chain risk control and supply chain integration capabilities. Therefore, based on the current situation of Pakistan's leather product industry transitioning from traditional linear production mode to circular economy mode, this article takes circular economy as the background to explore the impact of green supply chain risk control on the improvement of supply chain integration capability, and thus its impact on enterprise performance.

A theoretical model of green supply chain integration capability is proposed, providing some theoretical basis for the research of green supply chain integration. From a practical perspective, managers of current enterprises attach great importance to the integration capability of green supply chains. Exploring the relationship between green supply chain risk control and supply chain integration capability can help enterprises improve their supply chain integration capabilities in production and operation, while also reducing supply chain risks. This can not only improve the operational performance of enterprises, but also enhance their environmental performance, enabling the rapid development of circular economy models in leather product manufacturing enterprises. At the same time, it is also a support and response to the construction of national ecological civilization.

Framework

This article explores the relationship between green supply chain risk control and supply chain integration capability in the leather product manufacturing industry from the perspective of circular economy, as well as the impact of integration capability on enterprise efficiency. In the practice of adopting a circular economy business model in the supply chain, environmental impacts have gradually increased the pressure on manufacturing enterprises, and the green supply chain of the leather product manufacturing industry is facing greater risks, which has a certain impact on the green development of the leather product manufacturing supply chain. Therefore, this article studies the green supply chain of leather product manufacturing industry based on the "3R principle" of circular economy. Although the circular economy has expanded from the "3R principle" to "4R", "5R", and even "6R principle" in some fields (Kiaušienė, Hladkova, & Makūnaitė, 2024; Nikolaou, Tsalis, & Vatalis, 2022).

Therefore, this article explores green supply chains based on the "3R principle" of circular economy. This article takes leather product manufacturing enterprises as an example, first combining the "3R principle" of circular economy with "according to the source of supply chain risk" and "according to the operation process of the supply chain", and dividing supply chain risks into green procurement risk, green manufacturing risk, and green sales risk. Therefore, this article mainly studies the impact of controlling these three risks on the integration capability of the supply chain. Secondly, in terms of the benefits generated by the green supply chain in the leather product manufacturing industry, this article mainly evaluates the performance of enterprises composed of operational and environmental performance. Operational performance refers to the evaluation of operational costs and corporate profits.

Environmental issues have always been considered a natural extension of quality problems, as poor-quality products and processes inevitably lead to environmental problems (Geissdoerfer, et al., 2017). The improvement of corporate environmental performance is the result of the joint efforts of environmental management and green supply chain management. In summary, from the perspective of the "3R principle" of circular economy, this article mainly analyzes the risks of the leather product manufacturing industry in three aspects: cooperation with green suppliers at the source of procurement, reducing raw material waste in production and manufacturing, and conducting green sales in cooperation with customers. The theoretical models and key assumptions of the green supply chain integration capability of the leather product manufacturing industry are proposed from three aspects: green procurement, green manufacturing, and green sales. Furthermore, the relationship between green supply chain risk control and green supply chain integration capability of the leather product manufacturing industry, as well as its impact on enterprise performance, are studied. The theoretical model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Theoretical Model of Green Supply Chain Integration Capability in Leather Product Manufacturing Industry

Hypothesis

(1) The impact of green procurement risk control on the integration capability of green supply chain in leather product manufacturing industry. When facing procurement risks, enterprises actively take measures to manage and control the risks, and further integrate external supply chain partners and internal departments (Rogetzer, Silbermayr, & Jammerneegg, 2019). Based on the above discussion, this article proposes hypothesis H1.

H1 : There is a positive correlation between green procurement risk control and the supply chain integration capability of the leather product manufacturing industry.

(2) The impact of green manufacturing risk control on the integration capability of green supply chain in leather product manufacturing industry. In order to reduce the green manufacturing risks discussed above, enterprises have improved their supply chain integration capabilities by managing and controlling these risks through deeper cross departmental integration (White, Wang, & Li, 2015). Based on the above discussion, this article proposes hypothesis H2.

H2 : The risk control of green manufacturing is positively correlated with the supply chain integration capability of the leather product manufacturing industry.

(3) The impact of green sales risk control on the integration capability of green supply chain in leather product manufacturing industry. In the process of managing and controlling green sales risks, enterprises will further integrate external supply chain partners and internal departments to improve the integration capability of the supply chain (Lin, Tan, & Geng, 2013). Based on the above discussion, this article proposes hypothesis H3.

H3 : There is a positive correlation between green sales risk control and the supply chain integration capability of the leather product manufacturing industry.

(4) The Impact of Green Supply Chain Integration Capability on Enterprise Performance in Leather Product Manufacturing Industry. The financial performance of enterprises is also improved through customer integration, as it creates new opportunities for sales, enables the sales department to better understand the market and customer needs, and increases enterprise revenue. Customer integration helps buyers participate in collaborative environmental practices, resulting in positive outcomes in the context of global supply chain management (Kim, & Chai, 2017). Only high-level integrated enterprises can have a positive impact on the environmental performance of the entire supply chain (Kima, Jungb, & Rontoc, 2012). Based on the above discussion, this article proposes hypothesis H4.

H4 : The green supply chain integration capability of the leather product manufacturing industry has a positive impact on corporate performance.

Results Analysis

Preparation

This article retrieved relevant literature from both domestic and international sources, and drew on existing mature scales to compile and modify the initial questionnaire. Then, after discussions and analysis with professors in the field and management personnel in related industries, some items of the questionnaire were adjusted, and the wording of the questionnaire items was repeatedly revised to ensure more accurate and clear expression. Finally, a survey questionnaire for empirical research on the integration capability of green supply chain in the leathers industry was formed.

The survey questionnaire used in this article adopts the most commonly used 5-point Likert scale, with "1 → 5" indicating completely disagree, disagree, average, agree, and completely agree. Experienced managers from leather product manufacturing companies rate each item to express the satisfaction of respondents with their company's performance in green supply chain risk control, integration capabilities, and corporate performance. Table 1 is the measurement scale of this article.

Table 1. Measurement scale

Latent Variable	Number	Question items
Green procurement risk control (Chen, 2018)	GPRC01	High quality green suppliers
	GPRC02	Rapid response to interruptions in the supply of green raw materials
	GPRC03	Effective communication with green suppliers
	GPRC04	Stability of recycling channels for waste products
	GMRC01	Shorten the design time for green products
	GMRC02	Rapid response to sudden machine malfunctions

Green manufacturing risk control (Rostamzadeh, et al., 2018)	GMRC03	Pay attention to employee training to reduce raw material and energy waste
	GMRC04	Balance among green development of enterprises, production, and manufacturing
Green sales risk control (Colicchia, & Strozzi, 2012)	GSRC01	Accurately predict customer demand for green products
	GSRC02	Actively respond to inventory shortages caused by changes in demand
	GSRC03	Predicting market prices
	GSRC04	Timely prediction of changes in customer preferences
Supply chain integration capability (Syed, et al., 2019)	SCI01	Close cooperation between departments
	SCI02	Enterprise management is committed to environmental practices
	SCI03	Established long-term strategic partnerships with suppliers/customers
	SCI04	Share enterprise knowledge and information with supply chain partners

It can be seen in Table 1 that the four measurement items for risk control in green procurement in this article are: high-quality green suppliers, rapid response to interruptions in green raw material supply, effective communication with green suppliers, and stability of waste product recycling channels. The measurement scale for risk control in green manufacturing in this article consists of four items, namely shortening the design time of green products, responding quickly to sudden machine failures, focusing on employee training to reduce raw material and energy waste, and balancing the green development and production of enterprises. The measurement scale for green sales risk control in this article consists of four items, namely accurately predicting customer demand for green products, actively responding to inventory shortages caused by demand changes, predicting market prices, and timely predicting changes in customer preferences. The supply chain integration capability includes both internal and external integration capabilities of the enterprise. The internal integration capability of an organization is mainly reflected in the degree of cooperation between departments. External integration capability of supply chain refers to the coordination, communication, and cooperation ability between enterprises and supply chain partners, including the level of integration with suppliers and customers. Enterprise performance includes two aspects: operational performance and environmental performance. The measurement of corporate performance consists of four items, including reasonable cost, green product profit, carbon emissions, and consumption of harmful substances (Liu, et al., 2018).

Analysis

The distribution of the official survey questionnaire in this article with a total of 214 responses received. After removing invalid questionnaires, a total of 200 valid questionnaires were collected. The sample companies and respondents in this article are reflected through the years of implementing green supply chains, annual sales revenue, and the length of employment of the respondents. The basic information of the interviewed enterprises and respondents was sorted and analyzed, as shown in Tables 2, 3, and 4.

Table 2. Basic Characteristics of Sample Data and Duration of Implementing Green Supply Chain in Enterprises

Duration	Quantity	Proportion (%)
< 3 years	19	9.5
3-5 years	40	20
6-10 years	86	43
11-15 years	35	17.5
> 15 years	20	10

Table 3. Basic Characteristics of Sample Data and Annual Total Sales of the Enterprise

Duration	Quantity	Proportion (%)
< 1 million \$	11	5.5
1-2 million \$	23	11.5
2-5 million \$	25	12.5
5-10 million \$	48	24
> 10 million \$	93	46.5

Table 4. Basic Characteristics of Sample Data and Length of Service of the Respondents

Duration	Quantity	Proportion (%)
1-2 years	49	24.5
3-5 years	107	53.5
> 5 years	44	22

From Tables 2, 3, and 4, it can be seen that approximately 70% of the surveyed respondents have been engaged in green supply chain management practices for over 5 years in their leather product manufacturing companies. This indicates that most of the surveyed companies support the development of green supply chains, and the respondents have a certain level of knowledge and management practices in green supply chains. 46.5% of the surveyed companies have a total sales revenue of over 100 million yuan, indicating that there are many large enterprises among the surveyed companies. More than 70% of the respondents have more than 3 years of work experience, which further demonstrates that they are familiar with green supply chain management and can easily understand and objectively rate the questionnaire. At the same time, it also provides a certain guarantee for the reliability of the questionnaire data.

Since each variable must follow a normal distribution before conducting structural equation modeling analysis, it is necessary to first verify whether the collected data conforms to a normal distribution before conducting structural equation modeling analysis. Skewness and kurtosis are commonly used to test whether sample data conforms to a normal distribution. If both skewness and kurtosis are close to zero, then the research data follows a normal distribution. In general, the skewness coefficient and kurtosis coefficient are calculated to determine whether the sample data conforms to a normal distribution. If the skewness coefficient is between -3 and 3, and the kurtosis coefficient is also between -3 and 3, it is considered that the research data follows a normal distribution. Through SPSS 22 statistical software testing, as shown in Table 5. After calculation, it can be seen that the absolute value range of the skewness coefficient of the sample data in this study is 0.06~2.215, all less than 3; The absolute range of kurtosis coefficient is 0.409~2.468, all less than 3, indicating that the sample data in this article follows a normal distribution.

Table 5. Results of Normality Test for Sample Data

	N	Minimum value	Maximum value	mean value	Standard deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Standard error	Statistic	Standard error
GPRC01	200	1	5	3.11	0.82	0.01	0.17	-0.81	0.34
GPRC02	200	1	5	3.17	0.87	-0.14	0.17	-0.51	0.34
GPRC03	200	1	5	3.20	0.75	-0.14	0.17	-0.45	0.34
GPRC04	200	1	5	3.08	0.76	-0.01	0.17	-0.61	0.34
GMRC01	200	2	5	3.37	0.88	0.16	0.17	-0.68	0.34
GMRC02	200	2	5	3.47	0.76	-0.14	0.17	-0.36	0.34
GMRC03	200	2	5	3.37	0.85	0.12	0.17	-0.60	0.34

GMRC04	200	2	5	3.35	0.84	0.06	0.17	-0.63	0.34
GSRC01	200	1	5	3.58	0.86	-0.09	0.17	-0.31	0.34
GSRC02	200	2	5	3.56	0.83	-0.12	0.17	-0.62	0.34
GSRC03	200	2	5	3.41	0.93	-0.11	0.17	-0.62	0.34
GSRC04	200	2	5	3.68	0.85	-0.20	0.17	-0.31	0.34
SCI01	200	2	5	3.63	0.86	-0.19	0.17	-0.62	0.34
SCI02	200	1	5	3.39	0.88	-0.38	0.17	-0.62	0.34
SCI03	200	2	5	3.76	0.85	-0.20	0.17	-0.83	0.34
SCI04	200	2	5	3.64	0.89	-0.01	0.17	-0.54	0.34

According to Figure 1 and Table 5, it can be inferred that hypothesis H1 explores the relationship between green procurement risk control and the supply chain integration capability of leather product manufacturing enterprises. H1 assumes that green procurement risk control positively regulates the green supply chain integration capability of leather product manufacturing enterprises. The path coefficient between GPRC and SCI is 0.781, $p < 0.001$, The risk control of green procurement greatly promotes the improvement of the green supply chain integration capability of leather product manufacturing enterprises, assuming that the H1 verification result is supportive.

Assuming that H2 explores the relationship between green manufacturing risk control and the supply chain integration capability of leather product manufacturing enterprises, that is, the control of green manufacturing risks within the enterprise promotes the improvement of the supply chain integration capability of leather product manufacturing enterprises. The conversion path coefficient between GMRC and SCI is 0.524, $p < 0.001$, The risk control of green manufacturing greatly promotes the improvement of the green supply chain integration capability of leather product manufacturing enterprises, assuming that the H2 verification result is supportive.

Let spouse, H3 explores the relationship between green sales risk control and the green supply chain integration capability of the leather product manufacturing industry, that is, green sales risk control positively regulates the green supply chain integration capability of the leather product manufacturing industry. The path coefficient between GSRC and SCI is 0.508, $p < 0.01$, The green sales risk control positively regulates the level of green supply chain integration in the leather product manufacturing industry, assuming that the H3 verification result is supportive.

Presumptuous H4 has studied the relationship between supply chain integration capability and corporate performance, that is, the level of green supply chain integration capability of leather product manufacturing enterprises has a positive impact on corporate performance. The path coefficient between SCI and FP is 0.645, $p < 0.001$, Strengthening the green supply chain integration capability of leather product manufacturing enterprises can significantly promote enterprise performance, assuming that the H4 verification result is supportive.

Discussion

Against the backdrop of vigorously advocating the circular economy business model, this article studies the impact of green supply chain risk control in the leather product manufacturing industry on supply chain integration capabilities, and whether supply chain integration capabilities can improve enterprise performance. At the same time, this article provides a theoretical basis for the benefits of green supply chain integration for the green development of leather product manufacturing enterprises, and has certain guiding significance for the improvement of supply chain integration capabilities in enterprises. This article first summarizes and organizes relevant domestic and foreign literature, and extracts three potential variables from the literature, namely Green Procurement Risk Control (GPRC), Green Manufacturing Risk Control (GMRC), and

Green Sales Risk Control (GSRC). The relationship between these three latent variables and the integration capability of green supply chain was studied, and how the supply chain integration capability of leather product manufacturing enterprises implementing green supply chain affects their performance was explored. Then, drawing on mature scales from relevant literature, the measurement model and survey questionnaire of this article were designed. Leather questionnaires were distributed online to domestic leather product manufacturing enterprises, and a total of 200 valid data were collected. Finally, SEM statistical methods were used to verify and analyze the measurement model of this article. According to the verification results, GPRC, GMRC, and GSRC all have a positive regulatory effect on the green supply chain integration capability of the leather product manufacturing industry, and a higher level of supply chain integration promotes the improvement of enterprise performance.

(1) According to the verification results, this article found that green procurement risk control has a significant promoting effect on the improvement of supply chain integration capability (assuming H1 is true). Zhao et al. (2013) found through empirical analysis that supply delivery risks can disrupt supply chain integration. Due to issues from suppliers, such as difficulty in finding green suppliers, delivery failures, and raw material quality, procurement risks may arise during the implementation of the green supply chain, thereby affecting the integration of the green supply chain. In addition, according to the principle of "recycling" in the circular economy, recovering raw materials from the increasing amount of leather waste has become a way to reduce resource waste and protect the environment. However, the instability of the recycling channels for waste products (leather waste, semi-finished products, etc.) also increases the risk of green procurement (Min, & Galle, 2001). If the supplier cannot deliver the materials to the manufacturer on time, the manufacturer cannot deliver the products to the customer on time. The longer supply cycle provided by suppliers to manufacturers can lead to manufacturers passing on longer supply cycles to customers. In addition, delayed or failed delivery of raw materials can disrupt the production process, leading to delays in delivering products to customers and resulting in poor relationships between the enterprise and customers. In this situation, it is even more necessary to control the risks of green procurement.

(2) The research results show that green manufacturing risk control has a great promoting effect on the improvement of supply chain integration capability (assuming H2 holds true). The research results of Flynn et al. (2010) indicated that internal green manufacturing risks in enterprises, such as machine failures, employees' unfamiliarity with processes leading to non-standard operations, and longer green product design cycles, are key obstacles to green supply chain integration. In the process of transitioning from traditional production mode to circular economy production mode, applying the principle of "reduction and reuse" to green production process may bring new manufacturing risks such as imbalance between green development and production planning, unskilled operation of employees, and waste. In this situation, it is particularly important to control the risks of green manufacturing. In the process of green manufacturing, risk prevention and control can ensure the normal operation of enterprise production, which is more conducive to improving the environment and accelerating the green development of enterprises.

(3) The results of this article found that green manufacturing risk control has a promoting effect on the improvement of supply chain integration capability (assuming H3 holds true), which indirectly supports some of the research findings of Shah et al. (2024). The questionnaire results indicate that companies pay more attention to interacting with suppliers, but are not good at accurately measuring customer needs, cannot quickly adapt to changes in market prices, and cannot meet changes in customer tastes. Part of the reason is that manufacturers cannot accurately predict customer needs in a constantly changing market. Therefore, identifying and controlling the risks of green sales is an important way for enterprises to integrate their green supply chains. In the process of transforming the circular economy model, managing and controlling green sales risks through comprehensive collection of market information and improving demand forecasting capabilities is

beneficial for enterprise managers to make better decisions, actively respond to customer needs, and enhance the integration ability of enterprises with customers and within the green supply chain. Therefore, managing and controlling the sales risks caused by market demand uncertainty and fluctuations in green product prices can enable enterprises to actively integrate in green supply chain practices, thereby improving their green supply chain integration capabilities and placing them in an advantageous position in market competition.

In addition, the research results also indicate that GPRC and GMRC are more important than GSRC in influencing SCI levels. One possible reason may be that compared to the sales department, companies often do not have buffer policies for the procurement and manufacturing departments to deal with unexpected situations. For example, the impact of difficulties in extracting large amounts of funds in the face of emergencies will be directly transferred to the company's internal operations and downstream cooperation with customers.

(4) This article found that the improvement of green supply chain integration capability in the leather product manufacturing industry can to some extent enhance the performance of enterprises (assuming H4 holds true), which indirectly supports the research of Rani et al. (2024) and Power et al. (2005). In the circular economy model, enterprises need to pay attention to both operational performance and environmental performance. In order to ensure the smooth development of green supply chain, enterprises need to integrate green supply chain. By sharing information and resources, as well as effective cooperation between departments, enterprises can improve their internal integration capabilities, promote the rational utilization of internal resources, and further deepen internal cooperation. At the same time, it is more beneficial for the integration of enterprises with the outside world, promoting the overall improvement of supply chain integration capabilities. This is conducive to reducing the cost of green products, obtaining higher profits, and reducing carbon emissions and consumption of harmful resources, which helps to improve operational and environmental performance. Power believes that once a company implements supply chain integration, it will establish a communication network between different related members in the supply chain, and these members will meet each other's needs. Strengthening integration with suppliers and customers can enhance a company's production capacity and enable it to quickly adapt to the circular economy model. Therefore, cooperation between enterprises and external parties reduces the possibility of disrupting the normal operation of enterprises due to supply chain risks, reduces cost investment, and is beneficial for enterprises to move towards green development, resulting in an increase in the company's operational and environmental performance. In addition, if a company's green suppliers and customers are willing to share information resources with the company, share risks, and have a common vision of green development, it is beneficial to enhance the company's ability to integrate green supply chains, reduce operating costs, and increase company performance.

Conclusion

This article reviews literature on circular economy theory and green supply chain management, proposing a theoretical model to assess the integration capabilities of green supply chains in the leather product manufacturing industry under circular economy principles. A questionnaire survey of 200 leather product manufacturers was conducted to collect data, followed by empirical analysis to test the proposed model and hypotheses. The findings indicate that green procurement, manufacturing, and sales risk control positively influence supply chain integration capabilities, thus enhancing enterprise performance. The article contributes in two key areas. First, it integrates the "3R principles" of the circular economy into green supply chain practices, examining the relationship between risk control and supply chain integration in the leather manufacturing sector. This provides valuable insights for managers aiming to improve performance through green supply

chain integration and offers a theoretical foundation for advancing green supply chain management in Pakistan's leather industry. Second, the study concludes that improving green supply chain integration capabilities helps enterprises reduce costs, carbon emissions, and harmful substances, leading to both economic and environmental benefits. The integration of green supply chains not only boosts economic efficiency but also strengthens environmental management, enhancing competitiveness in the industry. Therefore, supply chain integration capability is seen as a key factor in gaining a competitive advantage in the transition toward green development.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no Declaration of Interest.

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